

COAGULATION OF COLLOIDS BY EXPOSURE TO HIGH FREQUENCY OSCILLATIONS.

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Results are given of the exposure of 14 sols to high frequency oscillations from a condensed spark discharge. Coagulation was copious in the majority of cases. The possible effects of intermittent cataphoresis and micellar orientation have been considered. Dielectric absorption and rectification of part of the input A. C. by the micella are suggested as additional factors.

Spring (*Bull. Acad. Roy. Belg.*, 1900, 483; *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1900, 19, 204) observed that discharges from electrodes *external to the liquid*, point discharges, etc. did not affect the stability of the lyophobic sols. Wilke and Muller (*Kolloid Z.*, 1933, 68, 257) using a more effective arrangement observed that the colour, viscosity, velocity of electrophoresis and electrical conductivity of the arsenious sulphide sol altered by applying a high frequency electro-magnetic field. In the course of an investigation in these laboratories, the results of which will be published shortly, on the viscosity of colloids subjected to electric fields due to alternating potentials at *low frequencies* (Joshi and Subbaiah, *Proc Indian. Sci. Congress, Chem. Sec.*, 1939, III, p. 50.), it was observed incidentally that with special precautions as to the experimental arrangements and an adequate source of energy; the sensitivity of a colloid to a wide range of frequencies of oscillations was appreciable, at any rate, in some of the systems investigated. The following experiments were, therefore, carried out to examine this phenomenon in some detail.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The colloidal solutions in water of a number of materials, listed herein, were prepared by the usual methods. 10 C.c. of each of these colloids at different concentrations were taken in an optical cell and exposed to emissions from a heavy condensed discharge of an induction coil of 12-inch spark length. The cell had, at a fixed distance from each other, two aluminium or platinum electrodes, of which one was earthed through an A. C. milliammeter of the rectifier type. The other was connected through a small capacity to an aerial, which picked up the high frequency oscillations produced by the discharge of the induction coil. The aerial current flowing through the colloid varied in the range 0.02 to 0.04 milliamper. (r. m. s.).

The time of exposure was kept constant at 5'0 minutes in all the cases. The following results were observed as to the producibility of coagulation amongst the colloids examined.

Sol.	Coagulation.	Sol.	Coagulation.
1. -ve Arsenious sulphide	Copious	8. -ve Manganese dioxide	copious.
2. „ Antimony „	„	9. „ Prussian blue	„
3. „ Sodium oleate (slightly alkaline)	„	10. „ Sulphur	„
4. „ „ „ (more alkaline than No. 3)	„	11. „ Cadmium sulphide	Slight
5. „ Copper ferrocyanide	„	12. „ Mercury „	Nil
6. „ Ferric hydroxide	„	13. „ Vanadic acid	„
7. +ve Ferric hydroxide	„	14. +ve Aluminium hydroxide	„

DISCUSSION.

The well known results on the cataphoresis of colloids suggest that coagulation might occur during the migration *en masse* of the charged micella towards the appropriate electrodes (*cf.* Thomson, *Nature*, 1921, 107, 520; Whytlaw-Gray, Speakman, and Thomson, *ibid.*, p. 619, 620). This, however, requires fields due to continuous potentials. The observations of Muth (*Kolloid Z.*, 1927, 41, 97) with a number of emulsions in water, Blüh on V_2O_5 suspensions (*ibid.*, 1925, 37, 267) show that an orientating influence obtains even under alternating electric fields. The relevant effects in so far as they are analogous to those in electrolysis may, however, be anticipated to be but small at high frequencies.

That the above considerations do not cover the entire picture is indicated by the fact that in our experiments the specific nature of the colloid material is also a factor, since coagulation does not occur in all the systems examined. Results with ferric oxide obtained indicate that the sign of the micellar charge is not a material factor. It is also interesting to see that while, for example, the V_2O_5 suspensions were markedly sensitive to the applied alternating field in respect of micellar orientation (Blüh, *loc. cit.*), the corresponding coagulating effect is but negligible (*vide* Table I), under the above conditions. It might be pointed out that experiments were also made with alternating currents of 50 and 500 cycles per second, to which, the colloid, contained in the annular space of a glass ozoniser of the Siemens' type, was subjected for half an hour at about 150 volts (r. m. s.) and by means of a transformer, 6000 to 8000 volts (r. m. s.); there was no sensible coagulation. Prolonged contact of the aluminium and platinum used as

electrodes had, however, no sensitising action. It is suggested that a *dielectric absorption* by the micellar material is possibly an important determinant of the coagulations thus induced. This dielectric absorption is known to be a function of (in fact almost always increases with) the frequency of the oscillations and of the nature of the material exposed. Presumably its influence is similar to that of light (Freundlich and Nathansohn, *Kolloid Z.*, 1921, 28, 258; Stintzing, *Koll. chem.-Beih.*, 1914, 6, 132; Schaum, *Wiss. Phot.*, 1913, 12, 93) and X-rays (Spring, *loc. cit*; Galecki, *Kolloid Z.*, 1912, 10, 149; Dhar, "Chemical Action of Light" 1931 p. 375-378) under which certain colloids are without effect, while others are sensitised or even stabilised. Similar results were observed by Joshi and co-workers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 217; 1937, 14, 254) in the "thermoageing" of a large number of colloids. It is also likely that depending upon the nature of the micellar substances, a part of the applied potential might be rectified and that the observed coagulation might, in part, be due to this rectified component.

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Received November 4, 1940.
